

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF DIGITAL DEVELOPMENT OF HUMAN CAPITAL IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

This article analyzes the state of digital development of human capital in Uzbekistan at the national level and the main trends in it. In particular, the changes in the educational system in the context of the introduction of digital economy and artificial intelligence, as well as the educational reforms implemented in this area, are analyzed in detail. In this study, empirical and conceptual studies related to the analysis of the state of digital development of human capital in the conditions of the introduction of digital economy and artificial intelligence, reflected in scientific sources in a number of online databases, were studied, and scientific approaches were systematized in them, and scientifically based proposals were developed for the further improvement of this field.

Keywords: state of digital development of human capital, digital development of human capital, artificial intelligence, digital human capital.

INTRODUCTION

Any method and approach needs changes over time. We cannot deny that this applies to human capital as well. It is in the context of the digital economy that the development of human capital is carried out on the basis of programs that develop digital skills in the educational system.

Artificial intelligence, one of the most important elements of the digital economy, is being widely implemented in many fields, including the field of education. UNESCO experts came to the following conclusions as a result of their research on the use of artificial intelligence in the field of education:

1. Artificial intelligence technologies can make education accessible to everyone (eg disabled, refugees, out-of-school). Robotics allows students with special needs to learn at home or even in the hospital.

2. As a result of the widespread introduction of artificial intelligence, the use of digital technologies will become a vital necessity in the near future. In this regard, educational institutions are required to make every effort to continuously improve the knowledge of their students in the field of artificial intelligence, taking into account these processes.

The introduction of artificial intelligence technologies into education began in the 1970s. At that time, researchers were working on solving the problem of providing education to each individual student with the help of computers. This research continued in several directions - to support education and assess students, as well as to introduce innovations to teachers and effective management of the educational system in order to support the educational process.

It is an important stage of the gradual development of knowledge within the framework of the formation of the trinity of the modern economy - "Knowledge economy", "Information economy" and "Post-industrial economy".

The processes of introducing artificial intelligence into education have the following characteristics:

- more than doubling of the number of educated people by 2030 mainly at the expense of developing countries;

- The rise of Asia, Africa and Latin America to the ranks of educational leaders;

- shift of qualification level assessment towards skills and ability to perform specific labor tasks;

- due to the increase in the weight of qualified employees in the labor market, the rate of increase in their income decreases;

- change of professions with the use of digitization and remote working opportunities;

- changes in demand and supply factors during educational services due to the increase in the share of alternative means of providing educational services (online platforms, open online courses and hakazos);

- transition to "Mobile education" using digital materials adapted for smartphones, tablets and other mobile devices;

- use of block-chain technologies for evaluation of educational results.

LITERATURE REVIEW

One of the leading economists in the field of labor economy K. Abdurakhmanov and his scientific team analyzed the changes in the labor market in the context of the introduction of artificial intelligence, and revealed the important aspects of human capital development for the competitiveness of enterprises in the context of automation of jobs [1]. Also, in the research of another local scientist, the institutional aspects of the development of human capital in the context of the digital economy were studied, and scientifically based proposals were developed for its further improvement [2]. The processes of rapid development of the digital infrastructure of educational institutions, training of personnel with modern digital competencies, updating of specialties and educational fields taking into account trends in the labor market, introduction of artificial intelligence systems into the educational environment were also covered by our

local scientists[3]. Another of the local scientists conducted research on the use of digital technologies in the education system, which is one of the important elements of human capital, and the introduction of new generation distance education systems [4].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, empirical and conceptual studies related to the issues of analyzing the state of digital development of human capital in the conditions of the introduction of digital economy and artificial intelligence reflected in scientific sources in a number of online databases were studied and scientific approaches in them were systematized. As a database for the research, the open sources reflected in the annual statistical publications of the Statistical Agency of Uzbekistan, the annual reports of relevant ministries and agencies were used. Also, systematic analysis, logic, induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, comparative analysis, monographic analysis and grouping methods were used in the research work.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Today, rapid digitization of educational materials and educational technologies can lead to a sharp increase in the share of qualified personnel worldwide. This, of course, leads to an increase in educational outcomes and skill requirements, as well as pay levels for each skill level. This reality makes it necessary to change the professional education system as soon as possible. Because the funding of national education systems, traditionally mainly by the state, should take this into account and be distributed taking into account national priority interests.

By 2030, global spending on education and training could reach \$10 trillion. Because the growth of population in developing economies due to the expansion of opportunities for labor mobility due to digitization corresponds to the increase in the amount of education and the increase in skills in different countries (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The volume of financial resources in the global market for educational services (US\$ billion) [5]

According to the World Bank, by 2030, the number of people who have received school education in Asia and Africa will reach 800 million, and the number of people who have completed doctoral studies will reach 350 million).

This will lead to an increase in the demand for educators, which will equal 100 million people in the labor market. The highest rates are expected in vocational education, which is largely due to the changing role of the teacher due to the increased demand for teachers. This makes it possible to take into account the size of shares in the educational services market.

The analysis of international academic mobility allows predicting the flow of labor migrants in the future, as well as the distribution of countries by global or regional priority.

In Uzbekistan, in recent years, the educational system has also been updated with the process of digital specialization. The establishment of special schools that allow preparing young people for digital skills from school age can be considered as an important direction of digital development of human capital. For example, special Al-Khorazmi schools and "IT" schools specializing in in-depth teaching of ICT and IT subjects can be taken as an example.

If in 2020, 14 main "IT" schools were opened, in 2021 another 86 such schools began their activities. By the end of 2023, the number of specialized schools is expected to increase to 205. That is, one can see from this picture that the coverage of digital education among the youth of the country has increased dramatically in recent years (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Number of schools specializing in IT [6]

There are 150 non-state educational institutions specializing in the field of "IT" in the territory of the republic, almost 70% of them are located in the capital.

There are 12 such centers in Tashkent region, 7 in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 6 in Khorezm region, 5 in Navoi region, 5 in Andijan region (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The number of non-state educational institutions in the field of "IT" as of 2022 [7]

These statistical data indicate that there are more educational institutions specializing in the field of "IT" in regions with developed digital infrastructure, and there are enough specialists in the field.

As for vocational education, according to the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation, it became known that information about graduates of

vocational colleges and vocational education institutions is recorded by their respective ministries. It became known that information about the graduates of colleges and vocational education institutions specializing in the field of ICT is recorded by the Ministry of Digital Technologies and the State Statistics Agency.

(Table 1)

Information about students of vocational and professional educational institutions in the fields of ICT [8]

Majors in IT	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	2020/2021	2021/2022
Computer technologies and informatics (thousand people)	157,418	118,519	59,117	11,808	3,357	3,200
Communication, information and telecommunication technologies (thousand people)	25,067	19,738	12,333	4,378	0,249	0,230

According to the official website of the State Statistics Agency, it provided information on the number of students in two majors: "Computer technologies and informatics" and "Communication, information and telecommunication technologies" in vocational colleges. Enrollment in colleges and vocational schools has declined over the past five years as the compulsory vocational education policy was abolished and the 11-year secondary education system returned. In turn, the coverage of educational areas in the field of ICT has decreased. However, due to the resumption of activities of some vocational colleges as professional educational institutions and technical schools, the number of educational areas in the field of ICT and the coverage of their students began to increase again.

According to the results of the research, the level of education of employees employed in the field of information technologies in the republic is distributed as follows, i.e., the largest share in this regard is secondary (50.0%), more than a third - higher (39.0%), and the smallest share - was found to consist of medium or incomplete medium (11.0%) categories. It is important to train personnel who are competent to develop and introduce artificial intelligence in the country. Therefore, it is desirable to create the necessary conditions for increasing the number of higher education institutions in this field and their level

of coverage.

The most important strategic task is to improve the quality and efficiency of the education system in Uzbekistan, to form modern knowledge and skills in students and young people, to ensure close cooperation and integration between educational systems and the field of science, and to ensure the integrity and continuity of education. Therefore, measures are being taken to prepare 21st century specialists on the basis of establishing a national education system that can withstand global competition, improving textbooks and training manuals based on modern requirements, creating a new generation of them, optimizing curricula and standards.

In the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026 and Digital Uzbekistan-2030 strategy, the tasks of increasing the number of graduates of higher educational institutions training personnel in the field of information and communication technologies, and graduates of secondary special vocational education institutions with an average level of competence in the field of information technologies are set. . As part of the implementation of these goals, new HEIs specializing in the field of "IT" were established. Among the existing ones, the number of artificial intelligence and "IT" areas and specialties has been increased (Table 2).

Table 2

HEIs training personnel in the field of "IT" and their educational directions and specialties [9]

№	Name of HEI	Bachelor	Masters
1	National University of Uzbekistan	4	7
2	Tashkent State Technical University	2	-
3	Tashkent State University of Economics	2	1
4	Tashkent State Pedagogical University	1	2
5	Andijan State University	2	1
6	Bukhara State University	2	1
7	Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology	2	2
8	Gulistan State University	1	1
9	Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute	1	-
10	Karakalpak State University	1	1
11	Karshi State University	2	-
12	Namangan State University	1	2
13	Namangan Institute of Engineering and Construction	1	2
14	Samarkand State University	2	1
15	Termiz State University	3	1
16	Urganch State University	1	-
17	Fergana State University	1	-
18	Jizzakh State Pedagogical Institute	1	1
19	Kokan State Pedagogical Institute	1	1
20	Navoi State Pedagogical Institute	1	1
21	Nukus State Pedagogical Institute	1	1
22	Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute	1	-
23	Tashkent University of Information Technologies (TATU)	10	21
24	TATU, Karshi	5	2
25	TATU, Nukus	5	2
26	TATU, Samarkand	5	2
27	TATU, Urganch	5	2
28	TATU, Ferghana	5	2
29	International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan	1	-

A post-graduate course in digital technologies and artificial intelligence has been opened at the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi and the Research Institute for the Development of Digital Technologies and Artificial Intelligence. A total of 33 target quotas have been allocated for basic doctoral studies and trainee-research in the field of artificial intelligence.

According to the information of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, more than 30 bachelor's and master's courses in the field of "IT" have been launched in existing higher education institutions within the framework of educational programs related to ICT. At the same time, the number of graduates in the 2021-2022 academic year increased by 78 percent compared to the 2016-2017 academic year.

Figure 4. The number of graduates from higher education institutions in the field of ICT [11]

The number of graduate students has also increased significantly - from 95 in the 2017/2018 academic year to 237 in the 2020/2021 academic year. In the academic year 2021/2022, this number was increased to 420.

In the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 17, 2021 "On measures to

create conditions for the rapid introduction of artificial intelligence technologies" No. PQ-4996, the list of HEIs and scientific organizations training personnel in the field of "Artificial intelligence" on the basis of a grant from the 2021-2022 academic year confirmed. (Table 3).

Table 3

The list of higher educational institutions and IT institutions, where the training of personnel in the field of "Artificial intelligence" will gradually begin on the basis of a grant from the 2021/2022 academic year [12]

T/p	Name of HEI	Admission parameters based on the scholarship and the start of the academic year			
		Bachelors	Study year	Masters	Study year
1.	Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi	30	From the academic year 2021/2022	10	From the academic year 2021/2022
2.	National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek	25	From the academic year 2022/2023	10	From the academic year 2021/2022
3.	Tashkent State Technical University named after Islam Karimov	25	From the academic year 2023/2024	5	From the academic year 2022/2023
4.	Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov	20	From the academic year 2022/2023	5	From the academic year 2021/2022
5.	Research Institute for the Development of Digital Technologies and Artificial Intelligence	-	-	10	From the academic year 2021/2022

Also, the list of 15 higher education institutions, which are expected to introduce training courses and subjects on the practical application of artificial intelligence technologies in economic sectors, social sphere and public administration system, was approved. Starting from 2021, a target allocation of 5 people per year for trainee-researchers and basic doctoral studies in the field of artificial intelligence has been established.

Also, ICT and artificial intelligence personnel training is being launched in non-state foreign and non-state Otm institutions. Among them are South Korea's Inha University in Tashkent, USA's Webster University in Tashkent, Italy's Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent, and India's Amity University in Tashkent.

In the last five years, the most introduced and most in-demand graduate programs in the labor market have been Telecommunications Engineering, Computer En-

gineering (Computer Systems Design), Information Security, and Software Development. Also, in the country, the system of retraining of specialists with skills in the field of "IT" is organized under the Ministry of Poverty Reduction and Employment, which includes special "IT" courses for unemployed citizens. Information on the retraining of "IT" specialists is provided by the Ministry of Poverty Reduction and Employment.

According to these data, as of 2022, more than 7,000 unemployed citizens across Uzbekistan have completed education, retraining or advanced training in the field of "IT" for 7 months, most of them in mobile robotics (11%), computer engineering (8.6%) and "Back-End Development" (8.3%) trained. In terms of regions, the largest share of participants corresponds to Fergana (11 percent), Namangan (10.5 percent) and Surkhandarya (9.1 percent) regions (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Courses for training, retraining and advanced training of unemployed citizens in the "IT" field, (%) [13]

Also, in January 2021, "IT-Park" signed a memorandum of cooperation with the Ministry of Poverty Alleviation and Employment, marking the beginning of the joint implementation of the "Future Skills Uzbekistan" project. The goal of this project is to increase the number of highly qualified "IT" specialists through a comprehensive training program on information technologies.

The project is aimed at improving the vocational education system in this direction. Within the framework of the project, about one hundred people from among school graduates, higher education entrants and

unemployed persons registered in the database of "Youth Register" will be trained in professions that are in high demand in the information technology market in every region of Uzbekistan. The project includes three main stages:

- professional education and training of "IT" specialists.
- Assessing the competences of an "IT" specialist and issuing a qualification passport.
- Helping an "IT"-specialist in finding a job and self-employment (freelancer).

Figure 6. The number of unemployed citizens retrained in the field of "IT", (%) [14]

From the data presented in Figure 6, it can be seen that the level of training of unemployed citizens in "IT" skills is high in Namangan and Fergana regions.

The country's "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy stipulates digital transformation of regions and networks, programs for introducing information systems, electronic services and other software products, organization of training in the basics of computer programming by covering 500,000 young people within the framework of the "One million programmers" project.

Based on this strategy, the "One Million Uzbek Coders" educational project was launched in 2019 with the support of the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, under the initiative of "IT Park" (Fig. 7).

A project in a similar format for remote training of programmers was launched in the UAE and was called "One Million Arab Coders". The project consists of free training of a wide range of population on the basis of distance education in digital technologies through a specialized online portal. The goal of the program is to train a generation of professionals in this field, to equip them with all the tools and programming skills. The project covers the four specialties most in demand in the world labor market: "Data Analyst", "Android Developer", "Front-End Developer" and "Full-Stack Developer". The general course for each of them is designed for 120 hours of training. The result of each level will be the preparation of laboratory work and the receipt of appropriate certificates.

Figure 7.

Distribution of the participants of the "One million Uzbek programmers" project by age structure, (%) [15]

To date, more than one million people have participated in the "One Million Uzbek Developers" program, of which nearly 500,000 have received a certificate of graduation, and nearly 700,000 have received a certificate of participation. 54.8% of them are men, 45.2% are women. In addition, the participants of the program are mostly young people under 30 years old (almost 84%), especially students aged 13-17 (73.2%). In terms of regions, the largest share of program participants corresponds to Andijan (16.75%), Namangan (15.52%) and Samarkand (14.13%) regions. The smallest share falls on Syrdarya, Kashkadarya and Bukhara regions.

Also, the task of gradually establishing more than 200 specialized schools for in-depth training of informatics and information technologies on the basis of existing educational institutions for the further improvement of the provision of electronic state services in the country, for the creative development of students and learning the basics of computer programming in all districts and cities [16].

This project provides distance education to the population through a special online portal. In the first phase, the project includes the following four specialties, which are in high demand in the global labor market:

- data analysis;
- Android - development;
- FrontEnd - development;
- FullStack - development.

The general course is designed for 120 hours of education. At the end of each stage, participants prepare laboratory work and receive special certificates. Graduates who successfully complete the course can compete for grants and continue their studies in one of the more than 100 Nanodegree programs on the Udacity platform.

If we focus on the information of the international scientific research organization, in 2020 Oxford Insights and the International Research Center published the third edition of the AI Readiness Index of Governments. The index assesses the readiness of governments to implement artificial intelligence technologies in the provision of public services to their citizens.

The US, UK, Finland, Germany and Sweden make up the top five of the ranking, reflecting that North America and Western Europe are the regions with the highest overall AI readiness scores. The lowest average indicators were recorded in the Central Asian region. Uzbekistan ranks 95th among 172 countries with 37,171 points (maximum score - 100) in the index lists.

The overall score is calculated based on ten indicators: Strategy, Governance and Ethics, Digital Potential, Flexibility, Coverage, Innovation Capability, Human Capital, Infrastructure, Data Availability and Quality. Each of the indicators is evaluated on a scale of 100 points. Overall, Uzbekistan scores below average for each indicator (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Government AI Readiness Index scores for Uzbekistan [17]

One of the most important indicators in terms of applying artificial intelligence technology is human capital. According to the Artificial Intelligence Readiness Index for Uzbekistan, this indicator is 34.31, which is very low compared to the assessment of this indicator by the leaders of the index. It is no secret that the implementation of artificial intelligence technologies in our country can be done only with the help of qualified specialists, and the application of artificial intelligence in various fields in the country can be done

only with the help of specialists trained in digital skills.

Taking this into account, the decree and decisions by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan", "On measures to further improve the infrastructure of the digital economy and the "Electronic Government" system", "Measures to further modernize the digital infrastructure in order to develop the digital economy" - on measures", "On additional measures to introduce the digital economy, electronic

government and information systems to the public administration of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "On measures to create conditions for the rapid introduction of artificial intelligence technologies", "Digital economy and on measures for wide introduction of electronic government", "on measures to improve the quality of education in the field of mathematics and development of scientific research", "On measures for further improvement of the educational system in the field of information technology, development of scientific research and their integration with the IT industry" have been adopted.

Ҳозирги вақтда жаҳоннинг ҳамма мамлакатларида таълим тизимига сунъий интеллект кенг жорий этилмоқда. ЮНЕСКО таълимга сунъий интеллектни жорий этишининг куйидаги тамойилларини илгари сурган, яъни, таълимда сунъий интеллектдан ҳамма учун бир хил ва тенг ҳуқуқли асосда фойдаланишни таъминлаш; сунъий интеллектдан таълим ва ўқитишни такомиллаштириш учун фойдаланиш; сунъий интеллект даврида тшлаш ва яшаш учун кўникмаларни ривожлантиришга ёрдам бериш; таълим материалларидан шаффофлик билан ва назорат қилинган ҳолда фойдаланишни таъминлаш[18].

In Uzbekistan, artificial intelligence is also being introduced to secondary schools. The Agency for the Development of the President, Creativity and Specialized Schools under the Cabinet of Ministers of the country in cooperation with the companies "Integrated Technology Laboratory LLC" and "INTELA EDUCATION UZBEKISTAN" is introducing modern information technologies into the education system. Within the framework of cooperation, it is planned to introduce blockchain and artificial intelligence technologies and information education systems (Digital Diplomas), distance (online) teaching (Moodle, Canvas, BlackBoard) and cloud technologies in presidential, creative and specialized schools.

Also, the Department of Introduction and Development of Artificial Intelligence Technologies has been created within the structure of the Ministry of Digital Technologies. On the initiative of the Ministry, 10 "Smart Schools" are operating in Fergana. The "Smart School" program was developed by local experts, including scientists and professors of Urganch branch of Urganch State University, Tashkent University of Information Technology, and "Mustafo Software" limited liability company. The "Smart School" program allows for the analysis of the effectiveness of the quality of education in schools, the transparency of the teacher evaluation system, and several other indicators with the help of artificial intelligence.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the rapid development of the digital economy is being widely implemented in education as well as in modern information and communication technologies, as well as in all industries and sectors. In particular, based on the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, the following activities will be implemented in order to improve digital skills in the field of education:

- to create opportunities for mastering digital skills by providing students with digital technologies at the initial stage of education, developing analytical and critical thinking, providing knowledge and skills to young people in the conditions of large-scale digital transformation that will be necessary in the future;

- creation and implementation of a single distance education platform in order to implement it in all areas of education in the future;

- making permanent changes to the main curricula of secondary schools in order to increase the general level of the use of digital technologies for students;

- introduction of highly effective international practice aimed at organizing studies in the field of technological professions and innovative activities into the educational system;

- to increase the number of graduates of higher education institutions training personnel in the field of information and communication technologies, graduates of secondary special vocational education institutions with an average level of competence in the field of information technologies;

- improving the methods of teaching informatics in secondary schools by encouraging the participation of organizations in the field of information technologies in educational processes;

- organization of laboratories for the application and study of "Internet of Things", robotics, artificial intelligence technologies in the relevant fields of higher education institutions, as well as the involvement of foreign enterprises in this field;

- digitization of educational materials in education by developing and providing support for the state uniform requirement for the use of digitalization formats of paper-based materials;

- development and promotion of scientific research works in the field of digital technologies, improvement of their organizational mechanisms;

- conducting republican contests and events that promote the creation of ideas and new technologies;

- development and determination of the direction of creation of new search systems, including solutions for search and identification of audio and video materials, use of semantics in search and retrieval of information, new technologies in the machine translation system, as well as development of new algorithms and technologies of machine learning;

- on the analysis of large-scale data sets and the collection of knowledge, including new methods and algorithms for collecting, storing and intelligent analysis of large-scale data, new methods and programs for distributing large-scale data, as well as new methods for predictive modeling of complex engineering solutions and conducting research and development work on software;

- creation of new high-level computing and data storage systems, including new parallel computing algorithms, new supercomputer technologies and programs, new communication technologies and interaction protocols, to increase fault tolerance and reduce the exchange time between system elements, as well as the exchange time between system elements conducting re-

search in the field of creating new programs for reduction, high-performance and reliable data storage systems;

- conducting scientific work on the development of algorithms of robotic complexes and human interaction, the improvement of the infrastructure of data transmission networks, built-in sensors and sensor networks, as well as the creation of software for the implementation of various models of providing "cloud" services;

- implementation of the mechanism of national staff qualification improvement in the field of digitization in cooperation with the centers of large international enterprises;

- further improvement of electronic educational resources for the preschool, secondary and higher education system, as well as ensuring the use of domestic and international educational resources;

- development of human capital, including development of specialized education and popularization of professions in the IT field, improvement of institutional conditions for IT enterprises and reduction of administrative barriers;

- introduction of innovative educational programs on digital transformation and new technologies into the school and preschool education system [19].

In the general education system of the country, artificial intelligence is developed in two directions:

- the first direction - the solution of various acquisition problems of students is considered. Artificial intelligence analyzes the knowledge of learners and informs teachers with their level of mastery;

- the second direction - ensuring control of students during tests and exams is considered. In this system, in case of violation of the rules, the artificial intelligence immediately informs the proctor - the specialist responsible for monitoring the test-taking process.

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